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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

The next decade presents a unique moment in the history of planetary astronomy. For the first time, we have the technologies at hand to discover and characterize a wide range of exoplanetary systems, possibly harboring true Earth analogues. The opportunity is no less than answering humanity's millennia old questions of "Are we alone?" and "How did we get here?". The best part: Canada can play a leading role in this historic endeavor, if we make deliberate strategic investments over the next decade. In this white paper, we lay out pathways to develop the necessary instrumentation in collaboration with national and international partners to address the most fundamental questions regarding the formation of planets, the diversity of planetary systems, and the frequency of life in the universe. We recommend critical investments in a portfolio of assets including high-dispersion coronagraphy instrumentation for the upcoming ground based 30-meter class telescopes, a strong (JWST-scale) Canadian involvement in the next generation space missions LUVUOIR or HabEx, and support for small and large space missions led by Canada. Importantly, while the science case of searching for biomarkers on rocky exoplanets presents the most stringent design requirements, the proposed instrumentation will also be ideal for the characterization of giant exoplanets, sub-Neptunes, and super-Earths and address a wide range of science questions in the coming decade.

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1 Introduction

The fascination of humans with discovering new worlds dates back to the dawn of civilization. From reaching the ends of the Earth in the last millennia, to exploring the edges of the Solar System in the last century, now we have expanded our exploration of new worlds to the rest of the galaxy. In the last decades we've not only discovered that other stars bear planets as well, but that out there lies a wealth of diversity in planetary systems. How did these planets form? Are any of them similar to our own Solar System? Do any of them harbour life? Now, for the first time in history, we are on the verge of being able to answer what humans have wondered since they were first able to look up at the night sky.

The drive to answer these truly fundamental questions has fuelled an immensely rapid growth in the field of exoplanets, with tremendous strides having been made in this direction within recent years. Canada in particular has been at the forefront of many 'firsts' in the field of exoplanets, sparking unparalleled attention by the media and general public: the first extrasolar planets discovered using precision radial velocities (Campbell et al., 1988; Mayor & Queloz, 1995), the first detection of an extrasolar planetary atmosphere (Charbonneau et al., 2002), the first directly imaged exoplanetary system (Marois et al., 2008), and the first inference of water clouds in the atmosphere of a habitable zone world outside our Solar System (Benneke et al., 2019).

Despite all these successes, one major limitation in our understanding of the tremendous sample of planets has been our ability to directly observe them. Of the more than 4000 exoplanets discovered to date, all except a dozen of young gas giant planets have been discovered through indirect detection techniques such as Doppler radial velocimetry, the transit technique, and microlensing. Our current dependence on indirect methods is because existing astronomical facilities do not allow the separation of the faint planet light from the bright host star at a sufficient contrast level except for self-luminous young giant planets at wide separation (Macintosh et al., 2015; Beuzit et al., 2019). No current direct-imaging facility in the world has the capability of finding true analogs to any of the eight Solar System planets if they were orbiting a nearby Sun-like star. This greatly limits our ability to efficiently characterize the detailed atmospheric compositions and their potential habitability. Even if the planet is transiting, which enables us to characterize the atmosphere, we remain inherently "blinded" by the photon noise of the star. Additionally, the transit and radial velocity techniques used to find the planets are greatly biased towards finding hot planets orbiting close to their host stars, where the extreme heat and irradiation from the host star hinder the formation of liquid water and complex molecules.

Fortunately, recent research in instrumentation has demonstrated a new pathway to directly detect and characterize distant exoplanets, both from space and from the ground. On the ground, by combining state-of-the-art high-contrast imaging (HCI) technology with a modern high-dispersion spectrograph (HDS), recent laboratory demonstrations and simulations (Mawet et al., 2019; Snellen et al., 2015) have shown that the faint light received from exoplanets can in principle be sufficiently isolated from the bright host star to directly detect and spectroscopically characterize a large number of nearby planets. Similarly from space, NASA's concept studies LUVOIR and HabEx have demonstrated the feasibility of space missions that are able to detect and characterize true Earth analogs around a statistically significant sample of nearby Sun-like stars.

1.1 Science questions and objectives for the next decade

Exoplanet science offers us the opportunity to answer fundamental questions about how our Solar System fits among other planetary systems, such as: Is the Solar System unique? Are there many planets of similar size and composition to Earth? If so, how many of them may be habitable? And how many potentially habitable planets are inhabited? Broad questions like these also offer easy entry points to engage the general public in active research. We list below specific scientific objectives:

1. Understand the processes by which stars and their planets form, and how these processes shape the resulting system. Understand how planetary systems evolve over time by observing and characterizing protoplanetary disks, to debris disks, to \sim Gyrs-old mature systems, looking for signs of potential planet-disk interactions.
2. Use various characterization techniques to establish profiles of rocky planets, ice giants, and gas giants.

Characterize diverse targets to elucidate how each broad type of planet is impacted by orbital period, semi-major axis, insolation, spin rate, composition, atmospheric properties, etc.

3. Establish which parameters determine habitability and categorize biomarkers, including CH₄, CO, H₂O, and NH₃. Establish the impact of formation on habitability and characterize habitable zones of K and M dwarfs.
4. Determine potential biomarkers and test their observable impact on planetary atmospheres. Distinguish between potential biosignatures and false positives due to non-biological processes.

Importantly, many of our main science objective are in direct alignment with the ones identified by our international partners (e.g., [National Academies of Sciences, 2018](#)).

1.2 Two complementary pathways towards identifying biomarkers outside the Solar System

One of the big drivers for technological development for exoplanet science in 2020s is to extend characterization capabilities to rocky planets and find the “pale blue dots” in the solar neighbourhood. This is possible within the next 10–20 years, and with a large enough sample size, we aim to determine whether habitable, Earth-like conditions are rare or common in nearby worlds and then probe them for signs of life. This main science driver sets the most stringent technological requirement, and such an instrument capable of characterizing rocky planets to find the pale blue dots will address the above science goals.

Two complementary pathways towards identifying biomarkers outside the Solar System are possible. High-Dispersion Coronagraphy (HDC) for the 30-meter ground-based telescopes can be developed in a relatively short time frame (next 7–10 years). Such HDC systems aim at directly observing targets up to 10^{-8} planet-to-star contrast ratio at small angular separations (Figure 1 a) and probe potentially habitable worlds around the nearest M-dwarfs systems (Figure 1) and will likely provide our first opportunity to search for biomarkers on rocky habitable-zone planets outside the Solar System, possibly as early as 2026/27. Alternatively, the high-dispersion spectrograph could also be used to characterize transiting planets without extreme-AO. We will discuss the underlying technique, international efforts, and Canada’s unique know-how and opportunity in Section 2.

Figure 1: Complementarity between ground- and space-based observations. Earth-sized planets in the habitable zone of sun-like stars have planet-to-star contrast ratios of the of 10^{-10} . Such contrast ratios are currently believed to be exclusively possible from space with telescopes such as LUVOIR or HabEx (Section 3). The same planet in the habitable zone of an M-type star, however, would result in contrast ratios of 10^{-8} – 10^{-7} , albeit at at much smaller angular separation. Contrast ratios of 10^{-8} – 10^{-7} can realistically be achieved from the ground, and thanks to the 30+ meter diameter of next generation telescopes, the inner working angle can be small enough to image and characterize Earth-size planets around nearby M-stars with HDC systems (Section 2). Credit: O. Guyon

Figure 2: Target stars within 5 parsecs for characterization of habitable-zone planets as a function of distance from the Sun and planet-star contrast. The size of the circles indicates the angular separation between the star its habitable-zone as seen from Earth. Habitable-zone planets around M dwarfs (red) have a smaller angular separation, but more favourable planet-to-star contrast ratios than habitable-zone planets around Sun-like stars (yellow). Stars within the dashed curves present the nearest and most exciting targets for HDI and HDS systems on 30-meter class telescopes. Proxima Cen and Barnard's Star are even already known to have planets amenable to detailed characterization (Anglada-Escudé et al., 2016; Ribas et al., 2018). Credit: O. Guyon

Beyond that, characterizing a large sample of Earth-sized planets around Sun-like stars will be the domain of the next-generation flagship missions such as LUVOIR and HabEx. These space telescope concepts promise to deliver 10^{-10} planet-to-star contrast at sufficiently small inner working angles to determine whether habitable, Earth-like conditions are rare or common on nearby worlds. We will discuss these missions envisioned to be developed throughout the 2020s and early 2030s and Canada's role in Chapter 3. Finally, Section 4 will discuss space missions that support transiting exoplanet science. We present our recommendations to the Long Range Plan 2020 in Section 5.

2 High-dispersion coronagraphy as a near-term opportunity to search for biosignatures on habitable-zone exo-Earths around M stars

The first opportunity to directly search for biosignatures on potentially habitable zone planets will be provided by High-Dispersion Coronagraphy on the 30-meter class telescopes. To achieve this, we need to develop instruments that are specifically designed to determine the chemical composition of the atmosphere of exoplanets of all type, in particular nearby temperate Earth-like ones potentially hosting biological activity. These unique, powerful instruments will have the capability of measuring the spectral signature of water, carbon dioxide and biosignature gases such as molecular oxygen and methane. Comprehensive high technology development plan to enable what may well be the most important scientific discovery of the 21st century: the first evidence of biological activity (life) beyond the Solar System. This project will position Canada as a pivotal player in this exciting scientific endeavour. Instrumentation developed for 8 m and 10 m class telescopes can serve as pathfinders, while simultaneously opening a completely new parameter space for exoplanet characterization. In this section, we describe a plausible development pathway of already partially funded projects, where HISPEC/MODHIS would serve as a pathfinder on a 10-meter class telescope, ELT/HIRES would provide the first opportunity on a 30-meter class telescope to search for biosignatures in the 2026-28 time frame, and finally in the mid 2030s with TMT/PSI being the ultimate ground-based instrument to characterize exoplanets. All of these instruments would enable both transiting and non-transiting exoplanet science.

2.1 High-Dispersion Coronagraphy (HDC)

Coupling a high-resolution spectrograph (HDS) with a high-contrast imaging (HCI) instrument is the next big step in the direct characterization of exoplanet atmospheres. In this scheme, the high-contrast imaging system serves

Figure 3: Coupling a high-resolution spectrograph with a high-contrast imaging instrument is the next big step in the direct characterization of exoplanet atmospheres. *Upper Plot:* Diagram illustrating the instrumental and analytical process for atmospheric molecular detection using high-contrast imaging and high-resolution spectroscopy. *Lower Plot: Left:* Stellar PSF for conventional seeing = 0.6 arcseconds HDS observations with a contrast of 10^{-4} . *Middle:* Model PSF for HCI observations for an adaptive-optics assisted 8m telescope under the same seeing conditions. *Right:* Combining HDS and HCI allows to observe an exoplanet at a contrast which is the product of the individual HDS and HCI contrasts ($10^{-4} \cdot 10^{-3} = 10^{-7}$ for this model).

as a spatial filter to separate the light from the star and the planet, and the high-resolution spectrograph serves as spectral filter, which differentiates between features in the stellar and planetary spectra, e.g., between different absorption lines and radial velocities. The resulting high-dispersion coronagraphy (HDC) system has three game-changing benefits: detailed species-by-species molecular characterization, Doppler measurements (planet spin, orbital velocity, plus mapping of atmospheric and/or surface features), and last but not least, improved detection capability. This subsection provides a background on HDS and HCI and explains the benefit of combining them.

2.1.1 High dispersion spectroscopy (HDS)

High dispersion spectroscopy consists of spectrally splitting light into many different wavelengths, resolving broad molecular bands into thousands of individual spectral lines. These lines are not only unique to their chemical species but, for exoplanet atmospheres, are also Doppler shifted in wavelength during observations due to the change in the planet's radial velocity as it goes through its orbit. For exoplanets such as hot Jupiters that have orbital velocities of $> 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, this change in wavelength in the planet's light can amount to a change of multiple pixels per hour on a high resolution spectrograph. This shift in wavelength of the planet's signal can then be used to separate it from the much stronger, but quasi-stationary in wavelength, telluric and stellar lines that dominate the observed spectra. This splitting in the spectral dimension thus allows for the signal from each of these unique lines following exactly the planet's orbital path to be combined via cross-correlating with a model template, greatly enhancing the signal-to-noise and allowing for unambiguous molecular detections in exoplanet atmospheres (Brogi et al., 2013). HDS has been extremely successful in the last decade, robustly detecting a consortium of different molecules at a contrast level of $\sim 10^{-5}$ in the atmosphere of several exoplanets (Brogi et al., 2012; Birkby et al.,

2013; Piskorz et al., 2016; Birkby et al., 2017).

2.1.2 High-contrast imaging (HCI)

High-contrast imaging consists of spatially resolving a distant star-planet system in order to separate the two and directly observe the light from the planet. This can be done if the planet is located at a resolvable angular distance from its host star, and if the stellar light can be reduced at the position of the planet by several orders of magnitude, using a coronagraph and adaptive optics. If done at multiple different wavelengths bands, this can lead to estimates on the planetary effective temperatures, radii, and cloud content. With the help of post-processing algorithms to deal with the presence of quasi-stationary speckles, $\sim 10^{-6} - 10^{-5}$ planet-to-star contrast ratios can be reached using current 8m class telescopes (Macintosh et al., 2015; Beuzit et al., 2019).

2.1.3 HDC by combining HDS and HCI

Both HRS and HCI can reach very small planet-to-star contrast ratios for very different reasons. HDS achieves this by *spectrally* filtering the light while HCI by *spatially* filtering the light, both techniques not being mutually exclusive. This then makes it possible to reduce the starlight at the position of the planet located at some angular separation from its host star by several orders of magnitude using adaptive optics and coronagraphy and subsequently filter the remaining starlight using high-dispersion spectroscopy. The reason this works is that the planet's signal is both spectrally distinct and localized while the stellar speckles that limit the contrast ratio achievable via HDI have the spectrum of the star over the whole field, making the spectroscopic distinction between the two straightforward. Hence combining HRS and HCI could, in principle, allow for a contrast ratio of $\sim 10^{-5} \times 10^{-5}$ to be reached (Snellen et al., 2015). A schematic an example toy model of how this can be achieved is shown in Figure 3. HCI+HDS systems will be uniquely capable of enabling the first direct detections and characterization of “ordinary” evolved exoplanets known to exist from radial velocity surveys and the ESA's ongoing GAIA space mission (Figure 1). The obtained high-resolution spectra of the planets will provide crucial information on the chemical diversity of planets in the universe, their formation and evolution histories, the atmospheric chemistry and cloud physics of new kinds of planets, as well as the dynamical processes that set the spin rate of planets. Altogether, the proposed high-dispersion coronagraph will provide an unprecedented view into planets outside our Solar System and help understand how the Earth and Solar System fit into the larger context.

2.2 HISPEC/MODHIS

HISPEC/MODHIS is a proposed diffraction-limited spectrograph serving as a direct pathfinder and possibly science hardware for the MODHIS facility project (Multi-Object Diffraction-limited High-resolution Infrared Spectrograph) on the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT) (Mawet et al., 2019). HISPEC/MODHIS builds on diffraction-limited spectrograph designs such as NIRPS developed in Canada/France and Palomar-PARVI, both of which rely on adaptively corrected single-mode fiber feeds. Designed with TMT in mind, HISPEC/MODHIS would initially be tested and applied on the 10-meter Keck telescope and then move to TMT and serve as a possible third first-light instrument once TMT is constructed.

HISPEC/MODHIS will take $R > 100,000$ spectra of a few objects in a 10'' field-of-view sampled at the diffraction limit (10 mas scale), simultaneously from 0.95 to 2.4 μm (Y band to K band). This design makes it ideal for a wide range of high-dispersion spectroscopy application including transiting planets as well as high-dispersion coronagraphy for the most favorable planet targets. The scientific scope ranges from exoplanet infrared precision radial velocities, transit and close-in exoplanet spectroscopy (atmospheric composition and dynamics, RM effect), spectroscopy of directly imaged planets (atmospheric composition, spin measurements, Doppler imaging), brown dwarf characterization, stellar physics/chemistry, proto-planetary disk kinematics/composition, Solar system (e.g., comets), extragalactic science, and cosmology.

HISPEC/MODHIS features a compact and cost-effective design optimized to fully exploit the existing Keck-AO and future TMT-NFIRAOS infrastructures and boost the scientific reach of both Keck Observatory and TMT soon after first light. Seeing-limited high-resolution spectrographs, by virtue of the conservation of beam etendue,

Figure 4: Left: Simulated cross-correlation values of the detection of the CO_2 molecule in a Venus-like atmosphere of the Earth-sized planets Trappist-1b or c, combining data of 4 transits with HIRES. Right: Reflected light cross-correlation signal of the direct surroundings of Proxima Cen using high spectral resolution observations. The white spot at $\Delta \text{Position} = 0.48''$ shows the significant detection of the cross correlation signal of the terrestrial planet Proxima Cen b. The position of the host star is marked by a white cross. Figure adapted from HIRES Phase A executive summary.

grow in volume following a D^3 power law (D is the telescope diameter), and are subject to daunting challenges associated with their large size (e.g., mechanical and thermal stability). Diffraction-limited spectrographs fed by single mode fibers, on the other hand, are decoupled from the telescope input, and are orders of magnitude more compact and have intrinsically more stable line spread functions. On the flip side, their efficiency is directly proportional to the performance of the adaptive optics (AO) system. AO technologies have matured rapidly over the past two decades, becoming mainstream on current large ground-based telescopes and baselined for future extremely large telescopes.

2.3 ELT/HIRES

With first light planned in 2026/2027, ELT/HIRES will likely be the world's first instrument specifically designed to detect biosignatures in the atmospheres of potentially habitable exoplanets. The instrument will provide the unprecedented opportunity to enable what may well be the most important scientific discovery of the 21st century: the first evidence of biological activity (life) beyond the Solar System. With HIRES, this ground-breaking discovery will be within reach by the end of this coming decade. More generally, thanks to its unique capabilities, HIRES will enable a broad range of additional forefront scientific programs such as directly measuring the expansion rate of the universe, and put strong constraints on the time variation of physical constants. The HIRES baseline design is that of a modular fiber-fed cross dispersed echelle spectrograph which has two ultra-stable spectral arms—VIS and NIR—providing a simultaneous spectral range of 0.4-1.8 μm at a resolution of 100 000 with several, interchangeable, observing modes ensuring maximization of either accuracy, throughput or spatially resolved information.

The HIRES instrument is divided in several work packages (WP) whose assignment and responsibilities are currently being discussed within the HIRES consortium. Canada has the opportunity to join the HIRES project and become one of the major partners of the project. The Canadian WPs could naturally be defined by our strong expertise in the following instrumentation areas: adaptive optics, large format infrared detectors and cryogenic infrared optical sub-systems, and the four Infrared detectors of the infrared spectrograph. Those are the same Hawaii-4RG 4kx4k infrared detectors used in SPIRou and NIRPS for which our team has extensive experience in tuning and integrating into a focal plane assembly (FPA) with demonstrated sub-mK temperature stability. The cost includes the procurement cost of the detectors, FPA manufacture, integration and tests. The Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics (SCAO) module is a key sub-system of the HIRES front-end to enable the high-contrast imaging mode needed to study exoplanets in reflective lights. Canada is world-renowned in developing adaptive optics systems.

By joining the ELT/HIRES project, the Canadian astrophysics community would play a big role on what could become the first detection of biomarkers outside the solar system. It would stimulate new collaborations worldwide and attract the best scientists and students to our institutions, enable major technological breakthroughs, and keep Canadian industry and academia abreast with leading-edge technologies. The HIRES project builds upon a long tradition of worldwide excellence and fruitful collaborations in developing world-class astronomical instruments, both in space and on the ground. Our team has the required scientific leadership, technical skills, and management experience to make the HIRES project a resounding success.

HIRES' first light is predicted to be in late 2026, most likely well before the science operations of TMT. The bulk of funding to build HIRES will be engaged several years before first light. At its first light in 2024, the European Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) will be the largest ground-based telescope at visible and infrared wavelengths. The flagship science cases supporting the successful ELT construction proposal were the detection of life signatures in Earth-like exoplanets and the direct detection of the cosmic expansion re-acceleration. It is no coincidence that both science cases require observations with a high-resolution spectrograph.

2.4 TMT/PSI

Finally, the Planet System Imager (PSI), expected in the early 2030s at the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT), will be the culmination of these new technologies (Fitzgerald et al., 2019). Featuring an AO system, a coronagraph and an IFU on three distinct spectral bands (0.6-1.8, 2-5, 8-13 μm), this complex instrument will be able to combine HCI and HDS by relaying its output to three fiber-fed spectrographs, including existing ones like MODHIS (Section 2.2). The resulting HDS capabilities consist in a wavelength coverage from 0.6 to 5.3 μm at $R=100\,000$. Advanced speckle suppression techniques, including chromatic and polarimetric differential imaging, will be applied in real time to minimize the contamination from the star. This should lead to a final contrast of 10^{-8} at 0.6-1.8 μm and 10^{-7} at 2-5 μm . Significant research and development in the coming years will be needed to achieve to demonstrate these advanced techniques in the laboratory and on sky (see also Marois et al. 2019). However, finally, PSI contrast specifications combined with the unprecedented inner working angle of the TMT would allow for astrometric, photometric and spectroscopic analysis of non-transiting exoplanets in the < 5 AU orbit regime. More specifically, habitable zone exoplanets will be accessible to atmospheric characterization around M-dwarfs via reflected-light and around Sun-like stars via thermal emission. The instrument will also be designed to search for biomarkers on these planets.

2.5 Technology development in Canada

Over the last decade, Canadians have made significant high-contrast imaging developments in all main aspects of the field (Marois et al. 2019). Across Canada, researchers have been innovating in adaptive optics research, to designing more powerful real time computers with predictive controllers, to inventing a new generation of deformable mirror, to innovating new coronagraph focal plane masks, to developing new focal plane wavefront sensing methods, to developing zero noise visible/NIR detectors and pursuing their long legacy of developing state-of-the-art imagers and spectrographs. The recent establishment of the NRC NEW EARTH laboratory will enable new innovations in the field, and be the basis to validate the best approaches to combine all high-contrast technologies. The foundation is now in place for Canadians to play a leading role in the design and construction of future HDC/HDS instruments, from GPI upgrades to ELT instruments, such as MODHIS, HIRES, PSI and MICHI, and to providing key advance hardware for future space observatories such as HabEx and LUVOIR.

3 True Earth analogs around Sun-like stars with HabEx & LUVOIR

3.1 Mission concepts

NASA is contemplating four flagship missions as part of the 2020 Decadal Survey; given the backlog of flagship missions, these missions would not be expected to launch until mid-late 2030's. Two of these mission concepts,

Figure 5: Telescope size, aperture geometry, and coronagraph type all affect the expected detection yields of exo-Earth candidates. On the x-axis, the inscribed diameter is the diameter of the largest circle completely contained within the telescope aperture. The green, red, and blue curves show yields for different combinations of telescope aperture geometry and coronagraph type, more fully explained in the main text. The yellow curve shows the yields for a single starshade paired with a 4-m telescope. Credit: Stark et al. (2019)

HabEx¹ and LUVOIR², and are designed around the direct imaging of Earth-like planets orbiting in the habitable zone of Sun-like stars and searching their atmospheres for signs of life. In particular, both missions rely on high contrast imaging and spectroscopy of planets in reflected light (UV through NIR). These large mission concepts share similar science goals, but differ in ambition and quantitative scientific returns (Fig. 5). LUVOIR enables tight constraints on the occurrence rates of habitable conditions and signs of life, as well as a large portfolio of general astrophysics and Solar System observations. The two study teams have collaborated since their initiation, and are presenting a buffet of options for UV/optical/near-IR observatories that enable exoplanet studies and general astrophysics.

Two architectures have been considered for LUVOIR: LUVOIR-A has a 15-m diameter on-axis segmented primary mirror and four instrument bays, LUVOIR-B has an 8-m diameter off-axis segmented primary mirror and three instrument bays. The baselined HabEx architecture utilizes a 4-m, off-axis, monolithic primary design. An off-axis, monolithic primary is ideal for coronagraphic design, but monolithic mirrors greater than ~ 4 -m become impractical due to their weight and size, while off-axis design becomes prohibitive beyond about 10-m diameter.

Both LUVOIR and HabEx include a coronagraph for high-contrast imaging, as this has been shown to be the most efficient way to do reconnaissance direct imaging observations (starshades slew slowly). With the larger diameter of LUVOIR, a coronagraph is also the best way to characterize exoplanets, while for the smaller HabEx, a starshade is more economical. Another qualitative difference between the two experimental designs is that the high angular resolution of LUVOIR enables high-precision stellar astrometry, which can be used to very efficiently discover nearby planets and measure their masses and Keplerian orbital parameters. Planets discovered solely via direct-imaging, on the other hand, will have unknown mass.

3.2 Strategy in Canada to prepare for HabEx/LUVOIR and beyond

The Canadian Space Agency has so far supported observers on the science and technology definition teams of both HabEx and LUVOIR. But we should aspire to contribute hardware to such a mission, especially given a) Canada's historical strength in direct imaging (e.g., Marois, Lafrenière, Doyon, etc.), b) the strong domestic engineering capability to contribute hardware to the mission (e.g., NASA contracting with NUVU for WFIRST).

It is notable that the French space agency, CNES, was not satisfied in sending observers to the LUVOIR STDT meetings, and so designed a complete instrument contribution: POLLUX (a high-resolution UV spectropolarimeter). If the Astro2020 decadal survey decides in favour of HabEx or LUVOIR, then the CSA should contribute an instrument, as we did for JWST. The other instruments planned for LUVOIR include LUVOIR Ultraviolet Multi Object Spectrograph (LUMOS), High Definition Imager (HDI), and Extreme Coronagraph for Living Planetary Systems (ECLIPS). For HabEx, currently planned instruments include the Workhorse Camera, UV Spectrograph, coronagraph and focal plane wavefront sensor schemes, and the starshade. Obvious areas of Canadian strength

¹ HabEx Final Report

² LUVOIR Final Report

where we could contribute include the coronagraphs and NIR spectrographs, both of which are part of the critical pathway to biosignatures.

Lastly, we note that both NASA and ESA have in the past contemplated space-based thermal infrared interferometry as a means to directly image extrasolar Earths (TPF-I/Darwin). There have been efforts here in Canada to realise fundamental technologies in providing ultrastable virtual optical benches for interferometric imaging of extrasolar planets and/or gravity wave detection. This critical technology exploits robotic devices to maintain constant relative distances between satellites flying in formation (e.g., Ogundipe & Ellery).

4 Near-term space-missions for exoplanet characterization

4.1 ARIEL Mission

There is mismatch between the thousands of bright targets that TESS and other next-generation planet searches are discovering (Ricker et al. 2015) and the dozens of exoplanets that JWST will realistically characterize in its lifetime (Cowan et al. 2015). ESA's ARIEL mission, with its 1 meter primary mirror and 0.5—7.8 micron simultaneous spectroscopy, is an approved space telescope that is designed to overcome this mismatch and survey a large number of transit planets with hydrogen-rich atmospheres—from hot Jupiters down to warm sub-Neptunes. It is scheduled for launch in 2028 and will be stationed at L2. During its 4-year mission, ARIEL will study what exoplanets are made of, how they formed and how they evolve, by surveying a diverse sample of a thousand extrasolar planets.

The PI of ARIEL, Giovanna Tinetti, recently invited the Canadian Space Agency to join the ARIEL consortium, which currently includes three Canadian professors: Nicolas Cowan (McGill University), René Doyon (Université de Montréal), and Diana Valencia (University of Toronto). There are two hardware contributions that the ARIEL consortium is interested in outsourcing and which Canadian industrial partners are well positioned to contribute, namely the cryo-harness (IMP Group in Halifax, NS) and V-groove radiators (e.g., Honeywell Aerospace). The cost of either of these work packages is modest, on the order of a couple million euro. The Canadian industrial expertise to contribute these components was developed and proven in building the Near Infrared Imager and Slitless Spectrograph (NIRISS) for the James Webb Space Telescope. In fact, it is precisely the CSA's proven track-record with JWST-NIRISS that led the ARIEL consortium to seek Canadian participation in the mission. Canadian scientists have much to gain from involvement in ARIEL. The mission is of great interest to those of us who discover exoplanets and characterize their atmospheres.

4.2 ÉPPÉ Mission

ÉPPÉ (Extrasolar Planet Polarimetry Explorer) is a proposed concept for a microsatellite mission that would use time-resolved differential polarimetry to characterize known exoplanets (hot Jupiters, Neptunes, super Earths) and serve as a pathfinder for spectropolarimetric exoplanet biomarker detection. The differential polarimetry capabilities of ÉPPÉ would be uniquely sensitive to polarized scattered light (dust, clouds, haze). So far, ground-based polarimeters have struggled to reach the 1 part-per-million level of precision required to detect scattered light from an exoplanet. The notional ÉPPÉ concept consists of a polarimetry instrumentation payload with a 30 cm aperture operating in the 300-800 nm band from a 180 kg class spacecraft in low-Earth orbit. ÉPPÉ is currently being advanced under a concept study funded by the Canadian Space Agency (CSA).

4.3 POEP Mission

A Canadian led micro-satellite with an efficient photometer fed by a 15-cm telescope is capable of making significant contributions to exoplanet astrophysics. The Mission, provisionally named Photometric Observation of Extrasolar Planets (POEP), will obtain high duty cycle, ultra precise photometry of exoplanet host stars. The POEP instrument consists of a 15-cm telescope that feeds dual frame-transfer CCDs to obtain u-band and i-band imaging. POEP measurements will be used to discover potentially habitable worlds transiting stars cooler than the Sun and to characterize the atmospheres of exoplanets through detection of scattered light. Based on the Canadian MOST

microsatellite (Walker et al., 2003) a microsatellite with a prime mission dedicated to exoplanet astrophysics the POEP will discover potential habitable zone planets around cool stars, confirmation of transiting planets (e.g., Winn et al. 2011), transit timing (e.g., Miller-Ricci et al. 2008) and exoplanet scattering and reflectivity (Rowe et al., 2008). The POEP mission will uniquely complement a number of planned or proposed space based facilities including large missions such as JWST, CASTOR, PLATO and ARIEL. For example, JWST and ARIEL will provide spectroscopy observations in the infrared to study molecules in exoplanet atmospheres. The interpretation of these observations will require an understanding of the potential presence of clouds which limit the depth to which an atmosphere can be probed using techniques such as transit spectroscopy.

4.4 CASTOR Mission

CASTOR is a proposed Canadian flagship mission to fly a 1-meter UV space telescope. Exoplanet astrophysics can benefit from high-precision photometry from CASTOR. The large aperture and Sun-synchronous polar orbit add unique capabilities to study exoplanet transits and phase-curves with UV observations that no other facility can provide. UV/blue-optical observations will be critical for progress in this area, as this spectral region provides a unique window into the structure and composition of planetary atmospheres via Rayleigh scattering and molecular absorption. Rayleigh scattering measured from UV-transits and phase curves provides direct measurements of particle size distributions and insight into photo-chemical reactions related to the formation of clouds or ices. The UV bandpasses of CASTOR are ideally tuned to detect strong absorption of ozone though relative transit photometry by comparing transit depths in the UV, CASTOR bandpasses. CASTOR could furthermore be upgraded to include exoplanet imaging, when paired with a NASA provided starshade spacecraft to suppress starlight (Lisman et al. 2019).

5 Conclusions and Recommendations for the LRP2020

Fueled by the recent progress and the enormous prospects of exoplanet science in the coming years, a large fraction of new faculty hires in Canada’s astronomy community has been in exoplanet science. Since 2011 alone, Canada’s top astronomy institutions have hired Professors Björn Benneke (U of Montréal), Aaron Boley (UBC), Nicolas Cowan (McGill), Ruobing Dong (U of Victoria), David Lafrière (U of Montréal), Quinn Konopacky (U of Toronto), Eve Lee (McGill), Kristen Menou (U of Toronto), Stanimir Metchev (Western U), Jason Rowe (Bishop U), and Diana Valencia (U of Toronto). In addition, 2013 and 2014 led to the foundation of the Institute for Research on Exoplanets (iREx) at University of Montréal, the Centre for Planetary Sciences at the University of Toronto, the NRC New Earth laboratory, the Technologies for Exo-Planetary Science (TEPS) NSERC CREATE program, the McGill Space Institute heavily invested in exoplanet science, and the number of students in exoplanet science in Canada has exploded exponentially (iREx annual report).

Now, the 2020s present a unique opportunity in the history of humanity in that we have for first time the technology at our fingertips to directly answer the millennia-old questions “Are we alone?” and “How did we get here?”. **Canada is extremely well positioned to play a leading role in this historic endeavour if we make deliberate strategic investments in the next decade.** All ingredients are there in Canada: we spearheaded many technologies needed for the characterization of exoplanets, we have the scientific know-how and industry collaborations in place, and we have played a strong leadership role in exoplanet science from the start. As the Canadian exoplanet community, we make the following main recommendations:

1. Canada should make deliberate investments in the research and development to construct high-dispersion coronagraph (HDC) instruments for the 30-meter class telescopes. In all likelihood, these will be the first instruments capable of probing for biosignatures such as oxygen on habitable zone planets around our Solar System, specifically around nearby M-stars. Canada is one of the leaders in the necessary technologies, with NIRPS likely being the first ultra-stable, AO-fed NIR spectrograph coming online in 2020 and Canada’s heavy involvement in the development of the extreme-AO system for Gemini/GPI.

2. Canadian astronomers should begin conversations with our international partners to identify a key role for Canada in large NASA and ESA-led exoplanet missions. In the short-term, the CSA can make a modest hardware contribution to ESA's ARIEL mission, which will fly by the end of the 2020's. We should also support technological development in order to position ourselves to make a $\sim 5\%$ contribution to LUVOIR or HabEx, which would fly in the late 2030's. As with the James Webb Space Telescope, Canada should take the leadership on a scientific instrument or key component of a multi-purpose telescope like LUVOIR.
3. In the medium term, it is of great importance to Canadian exoplanet community to continue the operation of CFHT/SPIRou or to find an equivalent telescope for its continued operation. As outlined in Section 2, the future of Canadian ground-based exoplanet research depends the know-how and instrumentation for high-resolution infrared spectroscopy. The proposed Maunakea Spectroscopic Explorer (MSE) and the nominal first-light instruments on the TMT are not ideally suited for exoplanet research and do not present an equivalent resource for the Canadian exoplanet community.
4. Finally, we recommend to build a balanced portfolio of small and large missions led by Canada including near term missions such as POEP, the development of the ÉPPÉ mission and to build capacity for flagship missions such as CASTOR.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

The initiative directly aims to answer humanity's millennia old questions of "Are we alone?" and "How did we get here?". The approach is to understand the conditions necessary to make a planet *Earth-like*. Observations across the electromagnetic spectrum obtained with a variety of techniques for a significant sample of extrasolar planets are required to determine their fundamental properties, including their interior structure, atmosphere, magnetic field and local stellar environment. The next generation of ground-based and space-based facilities have the potential to deliver transformational observations on this front; Canada can play a major role.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

The exact occurrence rate of small Earth-sized planets in the habitable-zone of nearby stars is not well constrained. This increases the uncertainty of how many stars would need to be investigated with LUVOIR/HabEx to be able to find and characterize a chosen number of potentially Earth-like planets. ESA's approved PLATO mission and the approved extended TESS mission will further address the occurrence rates of planets with longer orbital periods. Infrared RV surveys are also on the way to directly identify habitable-zone Earths around nearby mid- and late-M dwarfs.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Canada has a long legacy of leadership and breakthrough discoveries in infrared and high-resolution instrumentation for ground- and space-based telescopes. With University and industrial partners developing key new hardware and having the infrastructure to validate these on sky, the community is well positioned to play a leadership role in designing new instruments for current and future observatories. Continued development of Canada-led missions and instrumentation creates a unique environment to train HQP in scientific, technological and managerial aspects of a mission, thereby increasing Canada's capacity in the space sector and developing leaders of future missions. Our leadership participation in ground-based instruments such as SPIRou and NIRPS, and our planned participation in E-ELT HIRES, demonstrate capacity in Canada to contribute to the next generation of ground-based extremely large telescopes instrumentation, as well as interest from international partners to team up with Canada.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

This white paper is co-authored and co-signed by ~62 of the leading exoplanet scientists across Canada. The documents represents in large what the rapidly growing Canadian exoplanet community wishes to develop in the 2020s. Our scientific goals are well aligned with our international partners ([National Academies of Sciences, 2018](#)) and the development can build upon a strong history of academia/industry collaboration for HDS and HCI instrumentation (e.g., SPIRou, NIRPS, and GPI) as well as space mission hardware (e.g., JWST and MOST).

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Yes, strongly. Section 2 lays out a strategy for instrumentation projects (HISPEC/MODHIS and ELT/HIRES) that will strengthen Canada's leading role in the infrared and high-resolution instrumentation for exoplanets

characterization. It will set us up ideally to support instrumentation for the TMT in the 2030s. Similar, it is essential to start planning for LUVOIR/HabEx right now to establish ourselves as a JWST-like key partner in the coming 10-20 years.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

Through past and ongoing CFI funding, Canada has made substantial investments to develop the know-how and technologies to build world-class high-dispersion infrared spectroscopy instruments for 3–4 meter class telescopes (CFHT/SPIRou and NIRPS). These instruments have pushed the frontier of technology and achieve unprecedented infrared wavelength stability combined with simultaneous spectral coverage and high spectral resolution. Similarly, Canada has also been a major partner in the development of the Gemini Planet Image (GPI) which provided previously unseen high contrasts at small angular separation (HCI). It is this combination of know-how and experience across Canada that we can leverage to increase our participation and achieve a higher impact per unit of investment for instruments such as TMT/MODHIS, ELT/HIRES in coming years, and finally TMT/PSI in the 2030s. Also scientifically, continued Canadian would lead to consistency in science planning/investments: to harvest the scientific return of planet discoveries from SPIRou and NIRPS, investments should be made in instrumentation that can actually probe the planets they found. Not investing into exoplanet technologies now would leave the Canadian exoplanet community without access to state-of-the-art instrumentation when others begin the historic journey of searching for biomarkers and Earth-twins beyond the Solar System.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

None of the identified ground-based or space based opportunities (HDS, HCI, HISPEC/MODHIS, ELT/HIRES, TMT/PSI, POEP, EPPÉ, CASTOR, ARIEL, HabEx and LUVOIR) have secured complete Canadian funding to ensure either completion or direct participation. There is strong reliance on funding sources such as CFI or CSA grants/contracts. The total combined budget from all projects above exceeds the total envelop of both CFI and CSA Base-A funds over the next decade. The main programmatic risk is budget.

Canada has capacity for participation in all projects mentioned, thus, TRL is relatively high, but as with any new technology, especially for space, there must be avenues to raise TRL through low-cost opportunities such as balloon or small-satellite missions. For ground projects, established success from projects such as GPI and SPIRou clearly show excellent capacity and potential for growth.

Computational resources, although challenging, are being met through facilities such as Compute-Canada. However, the growing complexity of mission and data products needs be to be better understood and studied to better predict requirements over the next decade.

The lack of a Space-Program means that as a community we must be opportunistic. Funding for space is neither predictable nor stable. Thus, having a large portfolio of projects for Canadian participation or leadership is necessary which will enable the community to quickly react to rapid government decisions and funding opportunities.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

This program will be a continued demonstration of Canada's legacy of innovation, both technological and scientific, as we move forward to characterize Earth-like exoplanets. Canada can make contributions to both groundbased and spacebased facilities on short and long-term timescales. The size of the projects vary in cost and complexity from small to large.

For space, in the near term the development and launch of the Canadian-lead POEP mission will directly create well-paying middle class jobs in Canada, while also increasing Canadian capacity in the space sector by the training of HQP throughout the development and operations. Missions, of any size, that are led by Canada grow capacity for Canada to lead flagship missions. Developing technologies and missions in Canada allows for unique student interactions with industry and is strongly supported by government initiatives through the tri-councils. Canada needs mission specialists that are trained and retained in Canada. The EPPÉ mission is a potential small-to-medium sized mission that can immediately build on the success of a microsat mission that allows for additional HQP training and retainment of HQP.

There must also be Canadian participation in large international missions over the next decade. For exoplanet astrophysics, the priorities are ARIEL and participation in large missions such as LUVOIR or HabEx. Demonstration of Canadian capability to both lead and participate in missions on a variety of timescales and complexity is important. Exoplanet research pushes advancements in technology. Canada's leadership in the continued search for the answer to the question "Are we alone?" will inspire the next generation of Canadians to reach for the stars.

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